

Electrochemical detection of glucose on NiO nanosheets modified GCE

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Abstract : The sheet-like NiO nanostructures were prepared by a simple chemical precipitation method. The structure, morphology and composition of the product were investigated by XRD and SEM-EDAX analysis. The modified NiO ns/GCE was successfully employed as a sensor for glucose in alkaline medium based on the catalytic activity of the Ni^{II}/Ni^{III} centre and the electrochemical properties of the prepared nanostructures were investigated by linear sweep voltammetry (LSV), cyclic voltammetry (CV) and chronoamperometry (CA) techniques. The proposed sensor exhibited high catalytic activity towards glucose, high sensitivity with a linear range up to 1 mM, fast response time < 5 s, low detection limit, very good selectivity to glucose and stability.

Keywords : NiO nanosheets, chemical co-precipitation method, electrocatalytic, glucose sensor.

Introduction

In several points of view, glucose sensor have much interest ranging from medical applications of the blood glucose sensing to economical approaches^{1,2}. Though enzyme based sensor exhibits good selectivity and sensitivity, the drawbacks like thermal and chemical instability arises from enzymes due to its intrinsic nature³⁻⁵. To solve this problem, efforts are underway to develop and improve glucose sensors, particularly based on amperometric electrochemical method. Because of their unique electronic and catalytic properties, nanomaterials have been focused in many fields including analytical science⁶. Transition metal oxides based materials are of great interest for the electro-oxidation of glucose since a long time. Transition metal oxides such as ruthenium oxide, iridium oxide, manganese oxide and cobalt oxide are eligible to be electrode materials for the electrochemical detection of glucose^{7,8}. Though, the material exhibit excellent electrochemical properties, it belongs to the group of rare earth and hence economically not feasible. Among them, nickel oxide is the specific class of metal oxide nanostructure, having attracted a large attention due to their high electrical conductivity and low cost⁹⁻¹¹. In this present work, we report a simple co-precipitation method

to synthesis the NiO nanomaterials. The sheet-like structure was suitable to modify the glassy carbon electrode (GCE) for glucose sensing applications. These nanosheets were characterized by XRD and SEM-EDAX. The electrochemical determination of glucose was carried out by linear sweep voltammetry, cyclic voltammetry and chronoamperometry in 0.1 M NaOH electrolyte. The modified electrode shows high sensitivity, good selectivity and a wide linear range for glucose detection because of its electro catalytic activity and high surface area of NiO. Results suggested that NiO modified GCE could be used for non-enzymatic glucose sensors.

Experimental

Reagents : Nickel chloride and urea were purchased from SD-fine chemicals. Dopamine hydrogen chloride (DA), D-(+)-glucose, uric acid (UA), L-ascorbic acid (AA) and Nafion were obtained from Sigma chemicals.

Synthesis of NiO nanosheets : The sheet-like nickel oxide nanostructures were prepared based on an earlier report¹². In brief, nickel chloride (111 mg) and urea (288 mg) were dissolved in 100 mL distilled water. The mixture was stirred for 10 min, and then allowed to be in furnace at 90 °C for 48 h. The final precipitate was washed

with DI water and ethanol. This green colour precipitate was dried at 80 °C for 6 h to obtain the Ni(OH)₂ products. To get NiO nanosheets the as-prepared Ni(OH)₂ was kept at 300 °C for 5 h for thermal heat treatment at a rate of 1°C per min.

Equipments and electrochemical measurements : The morphological structure of the resulting NiO nanosheets was examined by field emission scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM) model (JEOL SM 840, Spain). The crystal structure and phase analyses of the as-prepared samples were characterized by powder X-ray diffraction (D8 Advanced, Bruker X-ray diffractometer, Germany) with CuK α radiation at an angle ranges from 20–80°. Electrochemical measurements were done using a CHI660C electrochemical analyzer (CH Instruments, USA) with conventional three electrode system, connected to the personal computer.

Results and discussion

Surface characterization of sheet-like NiO :

Fig. 1a, shows the typical XRD pattern of the synthesized samples. All the diffraction peaks in (black) can be assigned to the formation of Ni(OH)₂ by comparison with JCPDS file no. 73-1520. In curve (blue) the peaks with 2 θ of 37.09°, 43.29° and 62.9° correspond to the crystalline planes of the NiO nanosheets and the spectrum showed no trace of impurities. Using Debye-Scherrer equation, the crystalline size of the prepared nanosheets was calculated to be around 5 nm. SEM was used to identify the morphological structure of the synthesized products. Fig. 1b depicts the SEM image and the image shows that the sheet like morphology of NiO was well preserved. The EDAX measurements indicate that the nanostructures are composed of Ni and O, which again confirms the formation of pure NiO.

Electrochemical sensing of glucose :

The cyclic voltammograms of the NiO ns/GCE was demonstrated in 0.1 M NaOH solution with and without addition of glucose to test its electrocatalytic activity. Introduction of glucose into 0.1 M NaOH solution showed a remarkable enhancement in anodic peak current towards the catalytic oxidation of glucose observed in the potential range at 0.4–0.65 V (Fig. 2). The modified GCE displayed a pair of well-defined quasi reversible redox peaks due to Ni²⁺/Ni³⁺, with anodic and cathodic peak potentials at 0.6 V and 0.32 V, respectively. This represents that the sheet like nickel oxide greatly improved the performance of the electrode due to its large surface area and electron transfer ability.

According to the previous literature, the electrocatalytic oxidation of glucose to glucolactone could be due to the Ni^{II}/Ni^{III}. Hence Ni^{III} was specially proposed to act as an electron transfer mediator as indicated in the literatures. In addition, the effect of potential scan rate dependence currents in oxidation and reduction case were investigated in the scan rate range 20–500 mV/s.

Fig. 3a shows the CVs of NiO ns/GCE at various scan rates. Increment in scan rate causes the changes in the shape of CV curve, whereas the anodic and cathodic peak potential shifted towards more anodic and cathodic directions. The peak current in both cases are linearly proportional to the square root of the scan rate in the range 20–500 mV/s. This linearity explains that the redox reaction occurring on the electrode surface is due to the diffusion controlled process. In the redox process, where the reduction peak occurs due to the diffusion of OH⁻ ions from an electrolyte to electrode surface and the oxidation peaks occur to the diffusion of ions from electrode surface to electrolyte.

Fig. 1. (a) XRD-patterns of synthesized nanomaterials (blue-NiO, black-Ni(OH)₂). (b) SEM-images of NiO nanosheets. Inset shows EDAX spectrum of NiO nanosheets.

Fig. 2. CVs of NiO ns/GCE in the absence and presence of different concentrations of glucose (200, 400, 800, 1000 and 1200 μM) in (0.01 M) NaOH solution. Scan rate : 0.05 V s⁻¹.

Fig. 3. (a) CVs of the modified NiO ns/GCE at various scan rates in the presence of glucose (1 mM) containing NaOH solution. (Inset a) Plot of I vs $v^{1/2}$. (b) LSVs of 1 mM glucose at NiO ns/GCE in different concentration of NaOH solutions. (c) CA response of as-prepared NiO ns/GCE at various applied potentials upon the addition of glucose (100 μM) into 0.1 M NaOH solution.

To get a better sensitivity for the glucose detection, various parameters such as detection potential, detection pH (conc. of NaOH) were determined by changing the examined parameter while keeping the other fixed. The effect of pH on the oxidation current of glucose was studied at NiO ns/GCE electrode in a series of different concentration of NaOH solution by linear sweep voltammetry as shown in Fig. 3b. The peak current increased, when the concentration of NaOH was increased from 0.01 to 0.3 M. After 0.1 M NaOH, the peak current decreased. Hence, 0.1 M NaOH was chosen as the electrolyte solution due to its satisfactory response of current for 1000 μM addition of glucose. To know the optimum applied potential for amperometric detection of glucose, the amperometric current to various concentration of glucose was observed in the potential range between 0.4 and 0.6

V under stirring. In Fig. 3c, the maximum current response was observed at 0.6 V compared with other applied potential detection of glucose. Hence, based on the amperometric results, 0.6 V was selected to carry out the sensing of glucose with the modified electrode. Fig. 4a displays the CA response of NiO ns/GCE electrode under the optimized experimental condition.

The steady-state current response was reached within 5 s, for the addition of glucose at every 30 s under continuous stirring of electrolyte, indicating the fast amperometric response of the modified electrode. The amperometric current signal of NiO ns/GCE exhibits excellent linearity in the range 100 μM to 1000 μM (inlet

Fig. 4a) with the regression equation $I = 0.005x + 1.677$ and a correlation co-efficient of 0.9984. The sensitivity of NiO ns/GCE was 6.02 $\mu\text{A}/\text{mM}$ and the detection limit was 2.29×10^{-3} M mM. These results might be due to the electrocatalytic activity of the Ni^{II}/Ni^{III} redox couple and more effective electron transfer for the oxidation of glucose. In biological sample, some interferences such as dopamine, ascorbic acid and uric acid co-exist with glucose and hence it could be easily oxidized and interfere with glucose detection. Generally, the concentration of glucose (4–7 mM) is much higher than that of other interferences in real blood sample. Hence, the influence of 0.1 mM interference species on the current response of 1 mM glucose was evaluated. A remarkable current res-

Fig. 4. (a) Steady-state $i-t$ response of the NiO ns/GCE upon the successive addition of glucose solution : (Inset) the calibration curve for glucose detection. (b) Interference experiments measured of the modified electrode in 0.1 M NaOH at 0.6 V.

Table 1. Comparison of the NiO ns/GCE to other reported non-enzymatic glucose sensors

Modification on GCE	Electrochemical technique employed	Sensitivity	Linear range	Detection limit	Reference
NiCFP electrode	Amperometry	3.3 $\mu\text{A}/\text{mM}$	2 μM to 2.5 mM	1×10^{-7} M	13
NiO/GCE	Chronoamperometry	–	2 to 10 μM	0.3 μM	14
NiO ns/GCE	Chronoamperometry	6.02 $\mu\text{A}/\text{mM}$	100–1000 μM	2.29×10^{-3} M	Present work

ponse for glucose was obtained in Fig. 4b compared to other three interferences. These interference studies imply that the proposed NiO ns/GCE based sensor could be used for the sensitive and selective detection of glucose. Reproducibility of the modified electrode was investigated by calculating the RSD of the seven measurements with the addition of glucose (100 μM) using the same electrode and the calculated RSD was 2.78%. From the results, the modified electrode has excellent reproducibility. The comparison of NiO ns/GCE with different non-enzymatic glucose sensors are shown in Table 1.

Conclusion

In the reported work, sheet-like NiO nanomaterials was synthesized, characterized and used for non-enzymatic glucose sensor applications. The modified electrode (NiO ns/GCE) offered very attractive electrocatalytic activity towards glucose oxidation in alkaline medium and also showed a high sensitivity, excellent selectivity, low detection limit and good reproducibility to glucose. These characteristics indicate that the NiO nanosheets are promising materials for analytical purpose.

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